

Chimera: Optimizing Multi-Modal, Multi-Task GNN Architectures for Precision Neuroscience

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Abstract. Deep learning offers great potential for analyzing Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) data to advance our understanding of neurological disorders and guide intervention strategies. Recent work has incorporated graph neural networks to capture connectivity from structural and functional MRI; however, we identify three unresolved challenges: (1) multi-modal integration, (2) multi-task classification, and (3) underutilization of the rich architectural design space of graph operations. To address these gaps, we introduce *Chimera* - a hybrid N-branch GNN framework that combines classical encoder modules with graph operations for multi-modal, multi-task prediction. In our proof-of-concept, we deploy a three-leg, two-head architecture that merges resting-state functional MRI, MRI-derived morphology, and graph metrics into a unified latent representation. After cross-modal message-passing, the learned representations diverge into an age-regression and sex-classification head. When evaluated on 33,460 UK Biobank participants, Chimera achieves 92.2% accuracy in sex classification and a mean absolute error (MAE) of 4.21 years in age prediction. While some approaches with finer parcellations or temporal graphs achieve higher performance, Chimera offers a simpler, more versatile foundation for future development.

Keywords: UK Biobank · Graph neural networks · Multi-modal · Multi-task

1 Introduction

The human brain undergoes continuous remodeling over the lifespan—from early development and adaptive plasticity to age-related decline. Defining “typical” neurobiological inter-individual variability is non-trivial yet crucial for precision neuroscience, personalized biomarkers, and ultimately individualized intervention [2]. In recent years, deep learning has revolutionized this field. Models for neuroimaging, particularly functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI), have provided a rich toolkit of individual-level predictors across structural and functional domains. Specifically, graph neural networks (GNNs) have emerged to fuse these feature spaces with inter-regional connectivity. For example, STNAGNN

Fig. 1: Overview of the Chimera architecture for the UK Biobank. The Transformer, TCN, and GNN modules use configurable stages with L stacked blocks, while the MLPs follow a norm-act-dropout block structure; only GNN stages uses L_2 normalization.

applies spatio-temporal node attention for autism classification in task-fMRI [5] and DGA-DMIL’s brain-predicted age serves as biomarker of cognitive decline [6].

Despite many existing multi-modal toolkits, none simultaneously (1) integrate more than two imaging streams, (2) combine Euclidean-space transformers with non-Euclidean message-passing, (3) support both regression and classification, and (4) embed a meta-optimization for rapid architecture search. Here, we extend Azevedo *et al.*’s uni-modality model [1] within the GraphGym architecture [7] to propose *Chimera*, an N-modal GNN framework that unifies non-geometric encoders and geometric message-passing modules within a meta-optimization framework. In our experimental setup, we evaluate three modalities - morphological, temporal and connectivity - and test on two demographic tasks - age regression and sex classification, following prior approaches [1, 6, 5].

2 Data

We pre-processed MRI and resting-state fMRI (rs-fMRI) scans of 33,460 UK Biobank participants as in [1], parcellating each brain with the Desikan–Killiany atlas into 68 regions of interest (ROIs) to derive a graph representation of each individual’s brain, $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$, where $V = \{1, \dots, N_V\}$ and $E \subseteq V \times V$ encodes

Table 1: Overview of the feature space and architecture modules

Data modalities			
\mathcal{G}	Modality	d_M	Features
X_V	rs-fMRI	490	Time-series (six minutes) samples per ROI
X_V	Morphology	4	Volume, thickness, curvature, surface area
X_V	Graph metrics	6	Degree, betweenness, closeness, clustering coefficient, PageRank, node color
X_E	Edge features	2	Functional-connectivity weight, edge betweenness
Intra-layer GNN design choices			
Component	\mathcal{G}	Options	
Layer operator	(\mathcal{V})	GCN, SAGE, GIN, GINE	
Layer operator	$(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{V})$	General, PNA, GAT, GATv2, Transformer, Polynormer, GRIT	
Normalization	(\mathcal{V})	BatchNorm, LayerNorm	
Activation	(\mathcal{V})	ReLU, ELU, GELU, SELU, SiLU, PReLU, Tanh, Splines	
Dropout	(\mathcal{V})	Layer-Dropout	
Inter-layer GNN design choices			
Stage	$(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{V})$ stacking, SKIP-SUM, SKIP-CONCAT, GATED SKIP-SUM		

functional connections. Functional edges $e_k \in X_E$ are Pearson correlations between rs-fMRI time series, thresholded to the top 20%. We denote the node-feature matrix $X_V \in \mathbb{R}^{N_V \times M}$, edge-feature matrix $X_E \in \mathbb{R}^{|E| \times 2}$, and adjacency matrix $A \in \{0, 1\}^{N_V \times N_V}$, where M is the total number of node attributes (see *data modalities* in Table 1).

3 Architecture Design

Our model follows a three-branch Encoder-to-GNN design building on an extension for graph prediction within the GraphGym framework [7] (see Figure 1). In Module 1, each ROI $v \in V$ is encoded by: (i) an MLP for MRI-derived morphological features, (ii) an MLP for graph metrics — both preserving their original dimensions—and (iii) a linear upwards-projection of the rs-fMRI time series $t_i \in \mathbb{R}^T$ from 1 to d_p dimensions. We enriched d_p of t_i with *temporal* ($\text{PE}_{\text{time}} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times d_p}$) and *node-wise* ($\text{PE}_{\text{node}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_V \times d_p}$) sinusoidal positional encodings to distinguish time points and ROIs; with d_p being the node embedding depth over T . Formally,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{t}_i^{d_p} &= t_i^{d_p} + \text{PE}(t)_i^{d_p} + \text{PE}(v)^{d_p} \\ t_i^{d_{p'}} &= \text{Linear}(\tilde{t}_i^{d_p}) \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times d_p} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

To reduce rs-fMRI encoder complexity, we apply a one-layer 1D Temporal Convolutional Network (TCN) to segment each $t_i^d \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times d_p}$ into non-overlapping patches of the same dimension d_p . The stack of patches is encoded by the transformer and down-projected to $t \in \mathbb{R}^d$, such that all encoder embeddings X_V can be combined:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{X}_V^{(0)} &= [X_V^{\text{temp}} \parallel X_V^{\text{morph}} \parallel X_V^{\text{graph}}] \\ X_V^{(0)} &= \text{Linear}(\tilde{X}_V^{(0)}) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_V \times d} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In Module 2-3, the embedding vector is projected into node attribute space of d

dimensions and *node-wise* sinusoidal positional encodings are added to make the GNN ROI-aware before performing spatial message-passing over \mathcal{G} via a stack of L GNN layers in module 4. At each GNN layer $l = 1, \dots, L$, node attributes $X_V^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_V \times d}$ (and optional edge attributes $X_E^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{|E| \times 2}$) are updated by:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{X}_V^{(l)} &= \text{Layer}^{(l)}(X_V^{(l-1)}, X_E^{(l-1)}) \\ X_V^{(l)} &= \text{Drop}\left(\text{Act}(\text{Norm}(\tilde{X}_V^{(l)}))\right) \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

To mitigate over-smoothing, we can apply stage-specific GNN stacking strategies (Table 1). When using SKIP-CAT, each layer doubles the embedding dimension, which is then projected back to $\mathbb{R}^{N_V \times d}$ in module 5. In module 6 we aggregate all node embeddings via concatenation [1] and project the result to \mathbb{R}^d to form a single graph representation. Finally, this representation feeds separate regression and classification heads in module 7.

4 Experiment

We evaluated Chimera on 33,460 UK Biobank participants. All node attributes are scaled with Robust Scaler and stratifying data by age and sex into training (80%), validation (10%), and test (10%) sets. Age regression (Huber loss; $\delta = 2$) and sex classification (binary cross-entropy) were jointly optimized using exponential moving-average variance weighting.

We used a two-stage optimization combining Heteroscedastic Evolutionary Bayesian Optimization with Successive Halving. Stage 1 sampled 300 architectures across 17 components and three training hyperparameters, each trained up to 75 epochs with Ranger, step-decay, and early stopping. Stage 2 fine-tuned nine training hyperparameters via 150 additional configurations.

As shown in Table 2, the best candidate achieves a sex-classification AUC of 0.976 (\uparrow 5.6 pts) and accuracy of 0.922 (\uparrow 7.2 pts), surpassing Azevedo *et al.*. For age prediction, its MAE of 4.3 years ($r = 0.718$, $R^2 = 0.505$) falls behind DGA-DMIL (2.12) [6]. On the Human Connectome Project, Chimera outperforms STAGIN-SERO (88.2%) [4] and Brain-MS-G3D with 50 ROI’s [3], but is outperformed by STNAGNN (98.1%) [5] and Brain-MS-G3D with 200 ROIs (94.4%). Ablations show gains from fusing morphological and temporal modalities, but not from graph features.

5 Conclusion

We introduced Chimera, an N-modal GNN uniting classical modality specific encoders with message-passing models under a meta-optimization framework. Our framework outperforms existing GNNs on the Human Connectome Project and UK Biobank, though falls behind models leveraging dynamic connectivity and fine-grained parcellations [3, 5]. Therefore, future work could integrate spatio-temporal cross-attention for evolving time-graphs using high-resolution

Table 2: Test set and modality ablation performance of the best architecture.

Name	Modality	Task	AUC	Acc	MAE	r	R ²	Params
Azevedo <i>et al.</i>	temp	Sex	0.920	0.850	–	–	–	291,898
Ours (stage 1)	All	Dual	0.972	0.914	4.32	0.705	0.498	345,743
Ours (stage 2)	All	Dual	0.976	0.922	4.21	0.718	0.505	345,743
Ablation Modality								
Stage 2	morph	Dual	0.953	0.884	4.29	0.705	0.486	29,165
Stage 2	temp	Dual	0.942	0.868	5.13	0.549	0.294	322,428
Stage 2	morph+temp	Dual	0.978	0.926	4.16	0.727	0.518	322,528

parcellations or cortical meshes. Nevertheless, Chimera’s key contribution lies in its unified, extensible architecture that can be conveniently optimized.

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